

Parameterized Covariance Modeling for Non-Homogeneous and Non-Stationary Spatio-Temporal Random Processes on the Sphere

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Abstract

Identifying an appropriate covariance function is one of the primary interests in spatial and spatio-temporal data analysis because it allows researchers to analyze the dependence structure and predict unobserved values of the process. For this purpose, spatial homogeneity and temporal stationarity are widely used assumptions, and many parameterized covariance models have been developed under these assumptions. However, these are strong and unrealistic conditions in many cases. In addition, different statistical approaches should be applied to build a proper covariance model on the sphere. In this research, we introduce novel parameterized models of the covariance function for spatially non-homogeneous and temporally non-stationary random processes on the sphere. To alleviate the spatial homogeneity assumption and consider its spherical domain, this research applies the theories of intrinsic random functions (IRF) and considers the influence of time components in the model. A random process with stationary increments is applied to relax the assumption of the temporal stationarity. We also provide a methodology to estimate the associated parameters for the model. Finally, the simulation study demonstrates the validity of the suggested covariance model with its advantage of interpretability.

Key Words: Homogeneity, Stationarity, Spatio-temporal statistics, Covariance function, Sphere, Intrinsic random function, Random process with stationary increments, Integrated process

1. Introduction

Many methodologies for covariance modeling in spatio-temporal data analysis have been developed assuming Euclidean space with spatial homogeneity and temporal stationarity. Although there are many techniques and theories developed to relax the strong assumptions of homogeneity and stationarity on Euclidean space, those for spatial data on a sphere are relatively sparse. Spatial stochastic processes over the surface of a sphere need different statistical and mathematical approaches relative to those over Euclidean space. Huang et al. (2011) [5] claimed if models are built on the entire spherical space, great circle distances

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should be used instead of Euclidean distances. They also showed how to deal with non-homogeneous spatial data on the sphere by extending the application of intrinsic random functions, a flexible family of non-homogeneous models (Matheron 1973) [9]. Porcu et al. (2016) [11] also asserted that the spatial scale parameter is significantly affected by the choice of distances. They compared three different distance metrics available on the sphere and concluded that the chordal distance or Euclidean distance based on map projection can seriously distort and influence the estimation quality for the parameter compared to the great circle distance, particularly for a larger region on the sphere.

An important aspect of covariance modeling is how to parameterize the covariance functions. Obukhov (1947) [10] showed how to parameterize the covariance models on the sphere by using the assumption of spatial homogeneity. Roy (1969) [12] developed a covariance model for a spatio-temporal process by adding a stationary time term to Obukhov's model. Porcu et al. (2016) [11] tried two different types of covariance modelings for homogeneous and stationary spatio-temporal processes: adaptive models from the Euclidean case and models from direct construction on the sphere. The adaptive models are modified from models for Euclidean space. They basically replace the Euclidean distance argument with the great circle distance after an adjustment for a sphere. The models by direct construction are only valid for the great circle distance. According to their conclusion, direct construction is a more intuitive and flexible approach whereas the adaptive model requires stronger assumptions. Also, the adaptive model tends to allow only strictly positive correlations (Porcu et al. 2016). [11]

Our goal is to develop a parametric covariance function through direct construction on the sphere for spatio-temporal random process. Moreover, we also want to extend this approach to non-homogeneous and non-stationary random processes. In Section 2, we introduce the covariance model assuming spatial homogeneity and temporal stationarity with its interpretable structure. Section 3 relaxes the assumption of spatial homogeneity under the setting of stationary time terms. Then, the stationary assumption for temporal components is relaxed in Section 4. Section 5 describes a simulation study to show the validity and robustness of our methodologies to estimate the parameters.

2. Homogeneous and Stationary Spatial-Temporal Random Processes on the Sphere

2.1 Covariance Functions from Spectral Representation

Let $X(P, t)$ be a spatio-temporal process with $P \in \mathbb{S}^2$ and $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ where \mathbb{S}^2 is a unit sphere. Assume that the process is continuous in quadratic mean. We can expand such a random process through its spectral representation, which is convergent in quadratic mean (Yaglom 1961, Jones 1963, Roy 1969) [15] [8] [12]:

$$X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P)$$

where

$$Z_{\ell,m}(t) = \int_{\mathbb{S}^2} X(P, t) Y_{\ell}^m(P) dP$$

and the $Y_{\ell}^m(\cdot)$ are the real spherical harmonics such that

$$\begin{cases} Y_{\ell}^m(P) = \sqrt{\frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \frac{(\ell-m)!}{(\ell+m)!}} P_{\ell}^m(\cos \zeta) \cos(m\theta) \\ Y_{\ell}^0(P) = \sqrt{\frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi}} P_{\ell}^0(\cos \zeta) \\ Y_{\ell}^{-m}(P) = \sqrt{\frac{2\ell+1}{2\pi} \frac{(\ell-m)!}{(\ell+m)!}} P_{\ell}^m(\cos \zeta) \sin(m\theta). \end{cases}$$

In contrast to the spherical harmonics, each coefficient $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ is a function of time t and free from location P . The term $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ is longitude, and $\zeta \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ is latitude; therefore, $P = (\theta, \zeta)$. The function $P_{\ell}^m(\cdot)$ is the associated Legendre polynomials.

In this section, we assume $X(P, t)$ is homogeneous and stationary. Though the terms homogeneity and stationarity are often interchangeably, in this paper, we reserve homogeneity as a spatial term and stationarity as a temporal term.

Definition 2.1. A spatio-temporal process $X(P, t)$ is **homogeneous** and **stationary** if

$$Cov(X(P, t), X(Q, s)) = R(\overrightarrow{PQ}, |t - s|)$$

where

$$P = (\zeta_1, \theta_1) \text{ and } Q = (\zeta_2, \theta_2)$$

$$P, Q \in \mathbb{S}^2, \quad t, s \in \mathbb{Z}$$

$$\text{Latitude: } \zeta_1, \zeta_2 \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}], \quad \text{Longitude: } \theta_1, \theta_2 \in [0, 2\pi]$$

and $d(P, Q) = \overrightarrow{PQ}$ is the great circle distance between P and Q defined as

$$d(P, Q) = \arccos(\sin \zeta_1 \sin \zeta_2 + \cos \zeta_1 \cos \zeta_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2)).$$

Since the coefficients $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ are random variables, we need to compute their covariance function first to get a covariance of the process $X(P, t)$. Roy (1969) [12] showed that if a process is homogeneous and stationary, then the coefficients, $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$, are uncorrelated with each other in terms of the spatial components. This independence of the coefficients with respect to the spatial term allows us to express the covariance structure of a spatio-temporal process in a stationary form, which only depends on its time lag. As a result, we can express the covariance of the coefficients and that of the original process as (Roy, 1969)

[12]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_{\ell',m'}(s)\right) &= a_{\ell}(h) \\ \text{Cov}\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) &= \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}), \end{aligned}$$

where h is $t - s$, and $P_{\ell}(\cdot)$ is a Legendre polynomial.

The term $\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2\ell+1)}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h)$ should be finite because the second moment should be finite. Furthermore, $a_{\ell}(h)$ should be a positive semi-definite covariance function in terms of h . The covariance function of the process contains $a_{\ell}(h)$, which is a stationary function relative to temporal components. Therefore, we can parameterize the given covariance function by introducing a reasonable form of $a_{\ell}(h)$.

2.2 Parameterization of the Covariance Function

There are several approaches for the parameterization of covariance functions, such as separable model and some adapt models from Euclidean space to the sphere. However, our goal is to build a covariance function model that is not only intuitive and interpretable but also does not require strict assumptions. To achieve such a goal, a direct construction that considers the spherical domain and its geodesic distance can be a good choice. We can modify the model suggested by Yarenko (1983) [13] and derive the following form of a covariance function.

Proposition 1. Let $a_{\ell}(h) = g^{\ell}(h)$ where g is a continuous temporal covariance function. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_0(d, h) &= \gamma \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} g^{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos d) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\gamma(1 - g^2(h))}{(1 - 2g(h) \cos d + g^2(h))^{3/2}} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where γ is a scale parameter.

Proof. For $\phi_0(d, h)$ to have finite variance, one must have

$$\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2\ell+1)}{4\pi} g^{\ell}(0) < \infty.$$

By the generating function of Legendre polynomials,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2xt+t^2}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} P_{\ell}(x)t^{\ell} \quad (2)$$

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{-2x+2t}{(1-2tx+t^2)^{3/2}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \ell P_{\ell}(x)t^{\ell-1} \quad (\text{By taking } \frac{dg}{dt})$$

$$-t \frac{-2x+2t}{(1-2tx+t^2)^{3/2}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} 2\ell P_{\ell}(x)t^{\ell} \quad (\text{By multiplying } 2t) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1-t^2}{(1-2tx+t^2)^{3/2}} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (2\ell+1)P_{\ell}(x)t^{\ell} \quad (\text{By adding (2) and (3)}).$$

Now let $t = g(h)$, $g^{\ell}(h) = a_{\ell}(h)$, and $x = \cos d$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2\ell+1)}{4\pi} P_{\ell}(\cos d)g^{\ell}(h) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g^2(h)}{(1-2g(h)\cos d + g^2(h))^{3/2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Adding a scale parameter γ yields

$$\phi_0(d, h) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\gamma(1-g^2(h))}{(1-2g(h)\cos d + g^2(h))^{3/2}}.$$

□

The covariance function $\phi_0(d, h)$ in (1) is a function of spherical distance d and time lag h indicating homogeneity and stationarity as desired.

3. Non-Homogeneous Spatial-Temporal Random Processes on the Sphere

3.1 Non-Homogeneous Covariance Functions on the Sphere

In this section, we relax the assumption of the homogeneous spatial terms by applying the concept of intrinsic random functions. Intrinsic random functions (Matheron, 1973) [9] are generalized random processes, which can be used for the representation of non-homogeneous properties.

Definition 3.1. (Huang et al. 2019) [7] For $\kappa \geq 1$ and $\kappa \in \mathbb{Z}$, a continuous random process $X(P, t)$ on the sphere with finite second moments is an IRF_{κ} if and only if its low frequency-truncated process $X_{\kappa}(P, t)$ is homogeneous where

$$X_{\kappa}(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell}^m(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P).$$

We can see that when $\kappa = 0$, we have a homogeneous process. The concept of an intrinsic random function can be extended to spatial-temporal random processes. Let $X(P,t)$ be an intrinsic random function with stationary temporal terms. Then, $X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P) + X_{\kappa}(P, t)$ where $X_{\kappa}(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P)$. Now, define a nil space N such that

$$N = \text{span}\{Y_{\ell}^m(P) : 0 \geq \ell \geq \kappa, \quad -\ell \geq m \geq \ell\}.$$

By introducing the new basis of the nil space, $q_1(\cdot), q_2(\cdot), \dots, q_{\kappa^2}(\cdot) \in N$ such that $q_{\nu}(\tau_{\mu}) = I(\nu, \mu)$ for $1 \leq \nu, \mu \leq \kappa^2$ and $\tau_{\mu} \in \mathbb{S}^2$, we can re-express (Huang et al. 2019)

$$X(P, t) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\kappa^2} Z_{\nu}(t) q_{\nu}(P) + X_{\kappa}(P, t) \quad (4)$$

We denote the covariance function of $X_{\kappa}(P, t)$ as an intrinsic covariance function of order κ (ICF $_{\kappa}$). Since an ICF is homogeneous and stationary, we can use the same structure introduced in Proposition 1. That is:

$$\phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h) := \text{Cov}\left(\sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P), \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(s) Y_{\ell}^m(Q)\right) = \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}).$$

By using the structure of an ICF $\phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h)$ and the decomposition in (4), we can derive the covariance function of a non-homogeneous process $X(P, t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Cov}\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) \\ &= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \sum_{\ell'=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-\ell'}^{\ell'} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_{\ell',m'}(s)\right) Y_{\ell}^m(P) Y_{\ell'}^{m'}(Q) \\ &+ \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \sum_{\mu=0}^{\kappa^2} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_{\mu}(s)\right) Y_{\ell}^m(P) q_{\mu}(Q) \\ &+ \sum_{\nu=0}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\ell'=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-\ell'}^{\ell'} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\nu}(t), Z_{\ell',m'}(s)\right) q_{\nu}(P) Y_{\ell'}^{m'}(Q) \\ &+ \sum_{\nu=0}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=0}^{\kappa^2} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\nu}(t), Z_{\mu}(s)\right) q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, to build a proper covariance function of an intrinsic random function, it is crucial to introduce the appropriate covariance structures of the coefficients, such as $Z_{\nu}(t)$,

$Z_\mu(t)$, and $Z_\ell^m(t)$, which are the temporal random processes. Since $X(P, t)$ is an $\text{IRF}(\kappa)$ and not homogeneous, we cannot guarantee that the covariance functions of the coefficients, $Z_\nu(\cdot)$ and $Z_\mu(\cdot)$, are zero for $1 \leq \nu, \mu \leq \kappa^2$. That is, it is plausible and even more reasonable to assume that $\text{Cov}(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_\mu(s))$, $\text{Cov}(Z_\nu(t), Z_{\ell',m'}(s))$, and $\text{Cov}(Z_\nu(t), Z_\mu(s))$ are not zero when $\ell, \ell' \geq \kappa$; $\ell \leq m \leq \ell, \ell' \leq m' \leq \ell'$; and $t, s \in \mathbb{R}$. In other words, the coefficients $Z_\nu(t)$ s for $1 \leq \nu \leq \kappa^2$ are correlated with the other coefficients, which contrasts to the previous case of the homogeneous $X_\kappa(P, t)$. In fact, Huang (2016)[6] showed that the coefficients of the lower frequencies can be correlated with the other coefficients of higher frequencies through the example of the Brownian bridge, which is an IRF_1 on a circle.

In this paper, we aim to introduce appropriate structures for these covariance functions of non-homogeneous or non-stationary processes. In pursuit of this aim, we assume that the covariance functions of the coefficients have the following structures.

Proposition 2. Let $a_\ell(h)$ be positive semi-definite and be expressed with a form to the ℓ th power. That is, $a_\ell(h) = g^\ell(h)$. If we assume the structures of the covariance functions of the coefficients are such that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_{\ell',m'}(s)\right) &= a_\ell(h)I\{(\ell, m), (\ell', m')\} \\ \text{Cov}\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_{\ell,m}(s)\right) &= \text{Cov}\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_\nu(s)\right) = -a_\ell(h)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \\ \text{Cov}\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_\mu(s)\right) &= I(\nu, \mu) + \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_\ell(h)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\mu), \end{aligned}$$

then we can get the covariance function of an IRF_κ

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Cov}\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) \\ &= \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}, h)q_\nu(P)q_\mu(Q) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_\nu(P)q_\nu(Q) \\ &\quad - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}, h)q_\nu(P) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}, h)q_\nu(Q). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By the assumptions of the covariance structures of the coefficients and the Schur decomposition,

$$\begin{aligned}
Cov\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) &= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_{\ell}(h) Y_{\ell}^m(P) Y_{\ell}^m(Q) \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_{\ell}(h) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\mu}) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_{\ell}(h) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) Y_{\ell}^m(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(Q) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_{\ell}(h) Y_{\ell}^m(P) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}).
\end{aligned}$$

By the addition theorem,

$$\begin{aligned}
&Cov\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) \\
&= \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}) \right\} + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}) \right\} \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(Q) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_{\ell}(h) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}) \right\} \\
&= \phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}, h) q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}, h) q_{\nu}(P) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}(\overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}, h) q_{\nu}(Q).
\end{aligned}$$

□

This covariance function is positive semi-definite and its proof is in the appendix.

The next step is to model an intrinsic covariance function $\phi_\kappa(\cdot, \cdot)$. Since an ICF_κ is homogeneous and stationary, we can use the structure of the covariance function in Proposition 1 with the assumption that $a_\ell(h) = g^\ell(h)$. To allow more flexibility, we can add the scale parameters $\gamma, \gamma_\nu, \gamma_\mu > 0$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Cov}\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) \\
&= \gamma^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1 - g(h)^2}{(1 - 2 \cos(\overrightarrow{PQ})g(h) + g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell + 1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma_\nu \gamma_\mu) q_\nu(P) q_\mu(Q) \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1 - g(h)^2}{(1 - 2(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu})g(h) + g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell + 1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(P) q_\nu(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(P) \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1 - g(h)^2}{(1 - 2 \cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu Q})g(h) + g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell + 1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}) \right\} \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(Q) \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(1 - g(h)^2)}{(1 - 2 \cos(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu})g(h) + g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell + 1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}) \right\},
\end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma, \gamma_\nu > 0$, and $\tau_\nu, \tau_\mu \in \mathbb{S}^2$.

In sum, if we assume the structures of the coefficient covariance functions from Proposition 2, then we can build a proper covariance model for a spatially non-homogeneous intrinsic random function provided stationary temporal terms.

4. Non-Homogeneous and Non-Stationary Spatial-Temporal Random Processes on the Sphere

4.1 A Random Process with Stationary Increments and its Structure Function

So far we have assumed a stationary process for the temporal terms. However, just like spatial homogeneity, the temporal stationarity assumption is often too strong. We can relax this assumption by applying a random process with stationary increments and its structure function introduced by Yaglom (1958) [14]. Conceptually, these correspond to an intrinsic random function and its intrinsic covariance function, used in the previous section for the non-homogeneous spatial terms. In fact, the intrinsic random functions (IRF) are a particular case of the Guelfand generalized processes with stationary increments (Matheron, 1973) [9]. In this paper, we use the intrinsic random functions and intrinsic covariance functions for spatial terms and the random processes with stationary increments and structure functions for temporal terms for ease of understanding.

Definition 4.1. (Wei Chen et al. 2022; Yaglom 1958) [3] [14]

$\{X(t), t \in \mathbb{R}\}$ is called a random process with stationary increments of order $d \in \mathbb{Z}$ ($d \geq 0$) if $\Delta_h^d X(t)$ is stationary where

$$\Delta_h^d X(t) = \sum_{k=0}^d (-1)^k \binom{d}{k} X(t - kh), \quad t, h \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Additionally, $D(h_1, h_2)$ is its structure function where

$$D(h_1, h_2) = E \left([\Delta_{h_1}^d X(t)] [\Delta_{h_2}^d X(t)] \right).$$

This is symmetric and positive semi-definite.

Note that when $h = h_1 = h_2$, $D(h) = E \left([X(t+h) - X(t)]^2 \right)$ is a variogram. If $d = 1$, then $\Delta_h X(t) = X(t) - X(t-h)$; thus, $D(h_1, h_2) = E \left([X(t) - X(t-h_1)] \cdot [X(t) - X(t-h_2)] \right)$. Likewise, if $d = 2$, then $\Delta_h^2 X(t) = X(t) - 2X(t-h) + X(t-2h) = \{X(t) - X(t-h)\} - \{X(t-h) - X(t-2h)\}$. A stationary process corresponds to the case when $d = 0$. According to Brockwell and Davis (1991) [1], the order d of stationary increments usually stops at 1 or 2 in practice (Wei Chen et al. 2022) [3]. In this research, we mainly focuses on $d=1$. In the case of a discrete time series, that is, $t \in \mathbb{Z}$, the random process with stationary increments of order d is also called an integrated process $I(d)$, and we can achieve the following spectral representations.

Let $Y(t) = X(t+1) - X(t)$ where $t, h \in \mathbb{Z}$. Since $Y(t)$ is stationary (Yaglom, 1987) [16],

$$Y(t) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{i\omega t} dZ_y(\omega), \quad E(Y(t)) = c_1, \quad E(Y(t+h) \cdot Y(t)) = C_y(h) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{i\omega h} dF_y(\omega),$$

where $F_y(\omega)$ is a bounded non-decreasing function, c_1 is a constant, and $E(|dZ_y(\omega)|^2) = dF_y(\omega)$ for a random function with uncorrelated increments, $Z_y(\omega)$. Then, by the fact that $X(t+h) - X(t) = \sum_{s=t}^{t+h-1} Y(s)$, the following spectral representation is obtained:

$$D(h_1, h_2) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{(e^{i\omega h_1} - 1)(e^{-i\omega h_2} - 1)}{\omega^2} dF(\omega)$$

$$D(h) = 2 \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{(1 - \cos \omega h)}{\omega^2} dF(\omega) \quad (\text{when } h = h_1 = h_2),$$

where $F(\omega)$ is the spectral distribution function of $X(t)$. Similarly, for a continuous time series $X(t)$ when $t, h \in \mathbb{R}$ (Yaglom 1987) [16],

$$X(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (e^{i\omega t} - 1)dZ(\omega) \quad (5)$$

$$D(h_1, h_2) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (e^{i\omega h_1} - 1)(e^{-i\omega h_2} - 1)dF(\omega) \quad (6)$$

$$D(h) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \cos \omega h)dF(\omega). \quad (7)$$

If we assume that $X(t)$ is real and $X(0) = 0$, then a structure function $D(t, s)$ is equivalent to a covariance function $Cov(X(t), X(s))$ (Yaglom 1987) [16]. In other words, a valid covariance function of random processes with stationary increments $Cov(X(t), X(s))$ can be derived from a structure function.

Proposition 3. Let $X(t)$ be a real random process with stationary increments. Let $X(0) = 0$, and

$$a(t - s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega(t-s)}dF(\omega).$$

Then,

$$Cov(X(t), X(s)) = a(t - s) - a(t) - a(-s) + a(0)$$

where $a(\cdot)$ is a positive semi-definite covariance function.

Proof.

$$D(t, s) = E \left[\{X(t) - X(0)\} \{X(s) - X(0)\} \right] = E \left[X(t) \cdot X(s) \right] = Cov(X(t), X(s)).$$

Also, by the spectral decomposition in (6),

$$\begin{aligned} D(t, s) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (e^{i\omega t} - 1)(e^{-i\omega s} - 1)dF(\omega) \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[e^{i\omega(t-s)} - e^{i\omega t} - e^{-i\omega s} + 1 \right] dF(\omega) \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega(t-s)}dF(\omega) - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega t}dF(\omega) - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega s}dF(\omega) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dF(\omega) \\ &= Cov(X(t), X(s)) = a(t - s) - a(t) - a(-s) + a(0). \end{aligned}$$

□

Once the covariance function of $X(t)$ is achieved by Proposition 3, we can find the stationary covariance function by using the property of the integrated process $X(t)$.

Proposition 4. Let $X(t)$ be an an integrated process with $d = 1$ and $Y(t) = X(t + 1) - X(t)$. Then, a stationary covariance function of $Y(t)$ has a structure such that

$$Cov\left(Y(t), Y(s)\right) = 2a(h) - a(h + 1) - a(h - 1).$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} C_y(h) &= Cov\left(Y(t), Y(s)\right) = Cov\left(X(t + 1) - X(t), X(s + 1) - X(s)\right) \\ &= Cov\left((X(t + 1), X(s + 1)) - Cov\left(X(t + 1), X(s)\right) - Cov\left(X(t), X(s + 1)\right) + Cov\left(X(t), X(s)\right). \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 3, this equals

$$\begin{aligned} &a(t - s) - a(t + 1) - a(-(s + 1)) + a(0) - a(t + 1 - s) + a(t + 1) + a(-s) - a(0) \\ &\quad - a(t - s - 1) + a(t) + a(-(s + 1)) - a(0) + a(t - s) - a(t) - a(-s) + a(0) \\ &= 2a(t - s) - a(t - s + 1) - a(t - s - 1) \\ &= 2a(h) - a(h + 1) - a(h - 1). \end{aligned}$$

□

4.2 Intrinsic Random Functions with Temporally Stationary Increments

Now, we apply the random process with stationary increments to our spatial model for an IRF_κ . Hence, this process is both spatially non-homogeneous and temporally non-stationary. We will denote this process as $IRF(\kappa)/I(d = 1)$ or simply $IRF(\kappa)/I(1)$. For this purpose, we can replace $a_\ell(h)$ in Proposition 2 to $b_\ell(t, s) = a_\ell(t - s) - a_\ell(t) - a_\ell(-s) + a_\ell(0)$. Therefore,

$$Cov\left(Z_{\ell, m}(t), Z_{\ell', m'}(s)\right) = b_\ell(t, s)I\{(\ell, m), (\ell', m')\} \quad (8)$$

$$Cov\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_{\ell, m}(s)\right) = Cov\left(Z_{\ell, m}(t), Z_\nu(s)\right) = -b_\ell(t, s)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \quad (9)$$

$$Cov\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_\mu(s)\right) = I(\nu, \mu) + \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t, s)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu)Y_\ell^m(\tau_\mu). \quad (10)$$

Note that $b_\ell(t, s) = a_\ell(t - s) - a_\ell(t) - a_\ell(-s) + a_\ell(0)$. Then, since $a_\ell(h)$ is positive semi-definite and is expressed by a form of the ℓ th power, $b_\ell(h)$ is also positive semi-definite. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
Cov\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_\mu(s)\right) &= I(\nu, \mu) + \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t, s) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\mu) \\
&= I(\nu, \mu) + \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) - \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \\
&\quad - \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) + \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(0) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \\
&= I(\nu, \mu) + \frac{1-g(h)^2}{4\pi \left(1-2g(h) \cdot \cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) + g^2(h)\right)^{3/2}} - \frac{1-g(t)^2}{4\pi \left(1-2g(t) \cdot \cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) + g^2(t)\right)^{3/2}} \\
&\quad - \frac{1-g(-s)^2}{4\pi \left(1-2g(-s) \cdot \cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) + g^2(-s)\right)^{3/2}} + \frac{1-g(0)^2}{4\pi \left(1-2g(0) \cdot \cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) + g^2(0)\right)^{3/2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

As a result, if $a_\ell(h)$ has a form of $g(h)^\ell$, $Cov\left(Z_\nu(t), Z_\mu(s)\right)$ is free from spherical harmonics with orders bigger than κ .

Proposition 5. Assume the covariance functions of the coefficients $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ and $Z_\nu(t)$ have the structures in (8) - (10). Then, we can derive the covariance function of $IRF_\kappa/I(1)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
R(P, Q, t, s) &:= Cov\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) \\
&= \psi_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{PQ}, (t, s)\right) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} \psi_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}, (t, s)\right) q_\nu(P) q_\mu(Q) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_\nu(P) q_\nu(Q) \\
&\quad - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \psi_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}, (t, s)\right) q_\nu(P) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \psi_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}, (t, s)\right) q_\nu(Q) \\
&\text{where } \psi_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{PQ}, (t, s)\right) = \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, t-s) - \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, t) - \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, -s) + \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, 0)
\end{aligned}$$

The proof of Proposition 5 is very similar with that of Proposition 2, and it is presented in the appendix with the proof of its positive semi-definiteness.

4.3 Intrinsic Covariance Structure Functions

We can make an intrinsic covariance function on the sphere homogeneous by the low frequency truncation (Section 3). Likewise, in Section 4, temporal stationarity can be achieved by a difference (or differentiation) operator from an integrated process (or a random process with stationary increments). Considering these two properties together, we can achieve

a homogeneous and stationary spatio-temporal random process from an $IRF(\kappa)/I(0)$ by low frequency truncation and differencing (or differentiating).

Proposition 6. Let $X(P, t)$ be a spatio-temporal random process. That is, $X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P)$. Given a fixed location P , if $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ is an integrated process with $d = 1$, the random process $X(P, t)$ is also an integrated process $I(1)$. That is, $\Delta_1 X(P, t)$ is temporally stationary.

Proof. Let

$$X(P, t+1) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t+1) Y_{\ell}^m(P), \quad X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P),$$

and $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ be an integrated process of order 1. Then,

$$X(P, t+1) - X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \left(Z_{\ell,m}(t+1) - Z_{\ell,m}(t) \right) Y_{\ell}^m(P).$$

Denote

$$\Delta_1 X(P, t) = X(P, t+1) - X(P, t) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}(t) = Z_{\ell,m}(t+1) - Z_{\ell,m}(t)$$

$$\text{i.e., } \Delta_1 X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \left(\Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}(t) \right) Y_{\ell}^m(P).$$

Since $Z_{\ell,m}(t)$ is an integrated process with order 1, then $\Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}$ is stationary. Therefore, $\Delta_1 X(P, t)$ is also a stationary time series given P . □

For spatial non-homogeneity, the concepts of an intrinsic random function and its intrinsic covariance function are still applicable for an $IRF(\kappa)/I(1)$. Thus, spatial homogeneity still can be achieved by low-frequency truncation on the sphere.

Proposition 7. If $X(P, t)$ is an $IRF(\kappa)/I(1)$, then $\Delta_1 X(P, t)$ is an $IRF(\kappa)/I(0)$. In other words, $\Delta_1 X(P, t)$ is also an intrinsic random function with its order κ .

Proof. Let $X(P, t)$ be an $ICF(\kappa)/I(0)$ on the sphere. Then,

$$X(P, t) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P) + X_{\kappa}(P, t)$$

$$\Delta_1 X(P, t) = \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \{ Z_{\ell,m}(t+1) Y_{\ell}^m(P) + X_{\kappa}(P, t+1) \} \right\} - \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Z_{\ell,m}(t) Y_{\ell}^m(P) + X_{\kappa}(P, t) \right\}.$$

Let $\lambda \in \Lambda_\kappa$. Then,

$$\Delta_1 X(\lambda) = X_\kappa(P, t+1) - X_\kappa(P, t) = \Delta_1 X_\kappa(P, t).$$

Since $X_\kappa(P, t)$ and $X_\kappa(P, t+1)$ are homogeneous, $\Delta_1 X_\kappa(P, t)$ is also homogeneous. \square

By Propositions 6 and 7, we have that $\Delta_1 X_\kappa(P, t)$ is homogeneous and stationary if a random process $X(P, t)$ is an $IRF(\kappa)/I(1)$ on the sphere. Now, we need to introduce a reasonable structure for $Cov\left(\Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}(t), \Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}(s)\right)$. By using the structure in Proposition 3, we can find a proper stationary covariance function for $\Delta_1 Z_{\ell,m}(t)$. That is, $Cov\left(Z_{\ell,m}(t), Z_{\ell,m}(s)\right) = 2a_\ell(h) - a_\ell(h+1) - a_\ell(h-1)$ when $h = t - s$.

Proposition 8. We can get a homogeneous and stationary covariance function of $\Delta_1 X(P, t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} R_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h\right) &:= Cov\left(\Delta_1 X_\kappa(P, t), \Delta_1 X_\kappa(Q, s)\right) \\ &= 2\left\{\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ})\right\} \\ &\quad - \left\{\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h+1) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h+1) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ})\right\} \\ &\quad - \left\{\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h-1) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h-1) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ})\right\} \end{aligned}$$

By adding the scale parameter γ_0 , this yields

$$\gamma_0 \left[2\phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h) - \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h+1) - \phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h-1) \right]$$

where

$$\phi_\kappa(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1 - g^{2\ell}(h)}{(1 - 2 \cos \overrightarrow{PQ} \cdot g^\ell(h) + g^{2\ell}(h))^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}).$$

This homogeneous and stationary covariance function $R_\kappa\left(\overrightarrow{PQ}, h\right)$ will be called an intrinsic covariance structure function.

5. Simulation Study

In this section, we simulate an $IRF(1)/I(0)$ and estimate the parameters of its intrinsic covariance structure functions. For this simulation, we use $a_\ell(h) = \alpha^\ell e^{-\beta\ell|h|}$, which exponentially decays by h and satisfies the condition of the form $g^\ell(h)$. The simulation and estimation steps are:

1. Generate $X(\cdot, \cdot)$, an $IRF(1)/I(1)$, from multivariate normal $MVN(0, R(P, Q, t, s))$. The non-homogeneous and non-stationary covariance function $R(P, Q, t, s)$ is of Proposition 5.
2. Compute the homogeneous and stationary random process $\Delta_1 X_1(\cdot, \cdot)$ by truncating and differencing from the $X(P, t)$ generated from step 1.
3. Estimate the parameters of an intrinsic structure covariance function through Method of Moments (MoM) estimates and a numerical optimization with respect to the sum of squares between theoretical values and MoM estimates. For the numerical optimization, the quasi-Newton method is used through the R function *nlimb* (Gay 1990) [4]

To get the MoM estimates, let $\Delta_1 X_1(P, t)$ be a spatio-temporal process and assume $\mu = 0$. Then, its MoM estimator is (Bussberg 2020) [2]:

$$\hat{R}_\kappa(d_i, h_j) = \frac{1}{|N_{d_i, h_j}|} \sum_{\{(P, t), (Q, s)\} \in N_{d_i, h_j}} \Delta_1 X_1(P, t) \Delta_1 X_1(Q, s)$$

where $N_{d_i, h_j} = \left\{ \{(P, t), (Q, s)\} \mid d_i - \epsilon \leq d(P, Q) \leq d_i + \epsilon, \quad |t - s| = |h_j| \right\}$.

We want to find parameter estimates that minimize the sum of squares:

$$L(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_0) = \sum_{i=1}^{k_1} \sum_{j=1}^{k_2} \left[\hat{R}_\kappa(d_i, h_j) - R_\kappa(d_i, h_j, \alpha, \beta, \gamma_0) \right]^2.$$

That is, we want $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\beta}$, and $\hat{\gamma}_0$ that minimize the above loss function. The structure of the intrinsic covariance structure function $R_\kappa(d_i, h_j, \alpha, \beta, \gamma_0)$ is given in Proposition 8 with $a_\ell(h) = \alpha^\ell e^{-\beta\ell|h|}$ and a scale parameter γ_0 . For this simulation, we assigned the scale parameter $\gamma_\nu = \sqrt{0.1}$ (Proposition 5). This is because the basis function of the nil space $q_\nu(\cdot)$ tends to be far larger than the values of spherical harmonics $Y_\ell^m(\cdot)$. For example, when $\kappa = 1$, $q_1(\cdot) = 1$, but $Y_0^0(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \approx 0.2821$. Thus, unless we manipulate this scale parameter, we will overweight the non-homogeneous parts of the random process.

Table 1: Parameter estimates of 1,000 simulations with true parameter values for $IRF(1)/I(1)$ when $\gamma_\nu = 0.1$. Each simulation includes 200 locations and 20 temporal points. $a_\ell(h) = \alpha^\ell e^{-\beta\ell|h|}$

Simulation Result									
α	β	γ_0	$Avg(\hat{\alpha})$	$Avg(\hat{\beta})$	$Avg(\hat{\gamma}_0)$	$sd(\hat{\alpha})$	$sd(\hat{\beta})$	$sd(\hat{\gamma}_0)$	N
0.95	0.005	1.00	0.9174	0.0076	4.0785	0.0597	0.0062	3.3759	637
0.95	0.01	1.00	0.9107	0.0143	4.7058	0.0551	0.0096	3.2828	506
0.90	0.05	1.00	0.8632	0.0536	2.1632	0.0107	0.0148	0.6534	642
0.90	0.90	1.00	0.8677	0.5590	1.9977	0.0244	0.6814	1.3115	59
0.85	0.80	1.00	0.8239	0.8662	1.5936	0.0257	0.9187	0.7762	97
0.80	0.001	1.00	0.7816	0.0034	1.3695	0.0178	0.0026	2.0503	517
0.80	0.10	1.00	0.7791	0.1090	1.3946	0.0208	0.0427	0.5604	826
0.75	0.15	1.00	0.7273	0.1687	1.3848	0.0270	0.0761	0.6128	806
0.70	0.20	1.00	0.6769	0.2337	1.3644	0.0311	0.1202	0.6279	791
0.60	0.35	1.00	0.5766	0.4237	1.3509	0.0395	0.3003	0.6577	743
0.50	0.40	1.00	0.4740	0.5100	1.3546	0.0472	0.3372	0.7100	742
0.40	0.60	1.00	0.3675	0.7610	1.4637	0.0568	0.5630	0.8411	705
0.30	0.70	1.00	0.2565	0.8679	1.6579	0.0562	0.6251	1.0491	669
0.20	0.10	1.00	0.1644	0.1962	1.5400	0.0403	0.1644	1.4722	576
0.10	0.85	1.00	0.0591	1.0442	2.9495	0.0305	0.8595	2.2487	406

Table 1 represents the averages and standard deviations of the parameter estimates from the intrinsic covariance structure function for 1,000 runs of the simulation. Each simulation run included 200 locations and 20 temporal points. When the numerical optimization failed, the values of estimates were so extreme that the distributions of the estimates were severely skewed as shown in Figure 1, thus distorting the averages. To prevent this distortion, we eliminated the estimates of values that were zero or at least 10 times bigger than the true parameter values by assuming they occurred from failures of the numerical optimization. Figure 2 illustrates distribution of 826 estimates with $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.1$, and $\gamma_0 = 1$ after filtering out the failures. The true parameter values (red solid line) were close to the peaks of the density functions and the averages of the estimates (blue dotted line). The last column N in Table 1 indicates the number of estimates used to compute the average and standard deviation of the estimates after removing these failures. According to the results, the optimization process was most vulnerable to the situations when both α and β values were large. For instance, when $\alpha = 0.9$ and $\beta = 0.9$, only 59 among 1,000 estimates were left after failures were removed. Likewise, we had only 97 estimates for $\alpha = 0.85$ and $\beta = 0.8$. After excluding the failures, the estimates of α and β were relatively robust in that they were similar to the true values of the parameters as described in Table 1. The estimation of the scale parameter γ_0 worked differently depending on the other two parameter values.

We then obtained fitted values for the intrinsic covariance structure function by simply plugging the estimates into the covariance function formula in Proposition 8. Figure 3 and Figure 4 compare the MoM estimates, fitted values, and true values of covariances given that either time lags or great circle distances are fixed when $\alpha = 0.75$, $\beta = 0.15$, and $\gamma_0 = 1$. In this case, we conclude that our estimates of covariances were quite accurate in

Figure 1: Distributions of estimates before removing failures with $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.1$, $\gamma_0 = 1$, and $\gamma_1 = 0.1$. “true”(solid, red) means the true parameter value. “Avg”(blue, dotted) means the average of the estimates.

that the fitted values of covariances were close to the true values regardless of the distances and lags. As shown in the figures, the covariance values decayed as time lags or great circle distances increased. For instance, when the time lag $h = 0$, we can see the covariance decayed as fast as the great circle distances (spherical distances) increased (Figure 3). In addition, when the time lag was bigger than 5, the covariances were already almost zero regardless of the spherical distances.

6. Conclusion

We introduced parametric covariance models for non-homogeneous and non-stationary spatial temporal random processes on the sphere. Intrinsic random functions and random processes with stationary increments (i.e., integrated processes) enabled us to relax the homogeneous and stationary assumptions. Our novel covariance function model allowed us to understand the structure of the covariance and interpret the parameters as decay rates of covariances. The simulation study showed that the proposed model works properly for various parameter values. The structure of the proposed parametric models (Proposition 8) can be applied in more diverse ways by providing different formats for $\phi_\kappa(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $a_\ell(\cdot)$, which are an intrinsic covariance function and a time series covariance function, respectively. Then, the application of the model could be extended with more flexibility and adaptability.

Figure 2: Distributions of estimates after removing failures with $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.1$, $\gamma_0 = 1$, and $\gamma_1 = 0.1$. “true”(solid, red) means the true parameter value. “Avg”(blue, dotted) means the average of the estimates.

Figure 3: MoM estimates, fitted covariance values, and true covariance values for $\text{IRF}(1)/\text{I}(1)$ with $\alpha = 0.75$, $\beta = 0.15$, $\gamma_0 = 1$, and $\gamma_1 = 0.1$

Figure 4: MoM estimates, fitted covariance values, and true covariance values for $\mathbf{IRF(1)/I(1)}$ with $\alpha = 0.75$, $\beta = 0.15$, $\gamma_0 = 1$, and $\gamma_1 = 0.1$

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7. APPENDIX

7.1 Proof of Positive Semi-Definiteness in Proposition 2

Proof. To prove positive definiteness, we need to show that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \text{Cov} \left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j) \right) \bar{c}_j \geq 0 \quad \text{where } y_i, y_j \in \mathbb{S}^2, \quad t_i, t_j \in \mathbb{R} \text{ or } \mathbb{Z} \quad c_i, c_j \in \mathbb{C}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \text{Cov} \left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j) \right) \bar{c}_j \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \left\{ \gamma^2 \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell_2}^{\ell_2} a_\ell(h) Y_\ell^m(y_i) Y_\ell^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma_\nu \gamma_\mu) q_\nu(y_i) q_\mu(y_j) \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_\ell(h) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\mu) \right. \\
&+ \left. \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(y_i) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_\ell(h) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) Y_\ell^m(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(y_j) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_\ell(h) Y_\ell^m(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} a_\ell(h) \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j)
\end{aligned}$$

By Bochner theorem,

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{i\omega(t_i - t_j)} F_{\ell,m}(d\omega) \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j)
\end{aligned}$$

where $h_{ij} = t_i - t_j$, and $F_{\ell,m}(d\omega)$ is a non-negative measure.

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \int_{\mathbb{R}} F_{\ell,m}(d\omega) \sum_{i=1}^n c_i e^{i\omega t_i} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{c}_j e^{-i\omega t_j} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) \right\} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{c}_j \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) \right\} \\
&= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \int_{\mathbb{R}} F_{\ell,m}(d\omega) \left| \sum_{i=1}^n c_i e^{i\omega t_i} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \right|^2 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) \right\}^2 \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\text{Cov} \left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j) \right)$ is positive semi-definite. □

7.2 Proof of Proposition 5

Proof. Assuming the covariance functions of the coefficients have the structures in (8) - (10), by the Schur decomposition (Roy 1969) [12],

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Cov}\left(X(P, t), X(Q, s)\right) &= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_{\ell}(t, s) Y_{\ell}^m(P) Y_{\ell}^m(Q) \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_{\ell}(t, s) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\mu}) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_{\ell}(t, s) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) Y_{\ell}^m(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(Q) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_{\ell}(t, s) Y_{\ell}^m(P) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu})
\end{aligned}$$

By the addition theorem,

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}) \right\} + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}) \right\} \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(Q) \left\{ \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} b_{\ell}(t, s) P_{\ell}(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}) \right\} \\
&= \phi_{\kappa}\left(\overrightarrow{PQ}, (t, s)\right) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}\left(\overrightarrow{\tau_{\nu}\tau_{\mu}}, (t, s)\right) q_{\nu}(P) q_{\mu}(Q) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} q_{\nu}(P) q_{\nu}(Q) \\
&- \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}\left(\overrightarrow{Q\tau_{\nu}}, (t, s)\right) q_{\nu}(P) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \phi_{\kappa}\left(\overrightarrow{P\tau_{\nu}}, (t, s)\right) q_{\nu}(Q).
\end{aligned}$$

The scale parameters $\gamma, \gamma_{\nu}, \gamma_{\mu} > 0$ can be introduced to achieve more flexibility. Then, since we can express $a_{\ell}(h) = g^{\ell}(h)$, $\ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Rightarrow \gamma^2 \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(h)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{PQ})g(h)+g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \right. \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(t)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{PQ})g(t)+g(t)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(-s)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{PQ})g(-s)+g(-s)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \\
& \left. + \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(0)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{PQ})g(0)+g(0)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(0) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{PQ}) \right\} \right] \\
& + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma_\nu \gamma_\mu) q_\nu(P) q_\mu(Q) \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(h)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu})g(h)+g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \right\} \right. \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(t)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu})g(t)+g(t)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \right\} \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(-s)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu})g(-s)+g(-s)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \right\} \\
& \left. + \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(0)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu})g(0)+g(0)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(0) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{\tau_\nu \tau_\mu}) \right\} \right] + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(P) q_\nu(Q) \\
& - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(P) \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(h)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu Q})g(h)+g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}) \right\} \right. \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(t)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu Q})g(t)+g(t)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}) \right\} \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(-s)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu Q})g(-s)+g(-s)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}) \right\} \\
& \left. + \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1-g(0)^2}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{\tau_\nu Q})g(0)+g(0)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(0) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{Q\tau_\nu}) \right\} \right] \\
& - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(Q) \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(1-g(h)^2)}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu})g(h)+g(h)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(h) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}) \right\} \right. \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(1-g(t)^2)}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu})g(t)+g(t)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(t) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}) \right\} \\
& - \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(1-g(-s)^2)}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu})g(-s)+g(-s)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(-s) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}) \right\} \\
& \left. + \left\{ \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(1-g(0)^2)}{(1-2\cos(\overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu})g(0)+g(0)^2)^{3/2}} - \sum_{\ell=0}^{\kappa-1} \frac{2\ell+1}{4\pi} a_\ell(0) P_\ell(\cos \overrightarrow{P\tau_\nu}) \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma, \gamma_\nu > 0$, and $\tau_\nu, \tau_\mu \in \mathbb{S}^2$.

□

7.3 Proof of Positive Semi-Definiteness in Proposition 5

Proof. To prove the positive semi-definiteness for the covariance function, we want to show:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \text{Cov} \left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j) \right) \bar{c}_j \geq 0 \quad \text{where } y_i, y_j \in \mathbb{S}^2, \quad t_i, t_j \in \mathbb{R} \text{ or } \mathbb{Z} \quad c_i, c_j \in \mathbb{C}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \text{Cov} \left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j) \right) \bar{c}_j \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \left\{ \gamma^2 \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell_2}^{\ell_2} b_\ell(t_i, t_j) Y_\ell^m(y_i) Y_\ell^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma_\nu \gamma_\mu) q_\nu(y_i) q_\mu(y_j) \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t_i, t_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\mu) \right. \\ &+ \left. \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(y_i) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t_i, t_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) Y_\ell^m(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} (\gamma \gamma_\nu) q_\nu(y_j) \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t_i, t_j) Y_\ell^m(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} b_\ell(t_i, t_j) \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_j) - \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j) \end{aligned}$$

where $b_\ell(t_i, t_j) = a_\ell(t_i - t_j) - a_\ell(t_i) - a_\ell(-t_j) + a_\ell(0)$ and $a_\ell(\cdot)$ is a positive semi-definite function.

By the spectral representation in (6),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \left\{ \int_{\mathbb{R}} \{e^{i\omega t_i} - 1\} \{e^{-i\omega t_j} - 1\} F_{\ell, m}(d\omega) \right\} \\ &\left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_i) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} \left\{ \gamma Y_\ell^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu q_\nu(y_j) Y_\ell^m(\tau_\nu) \right\} + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i \bar{c}_j \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_\nu^2 q_\nu(y_i) q_\nu(y_j) \end{aligned}$$

where $F_{\ell, m}(d\omega)$ is a non-negative measure.

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \int_{\mathbb{R}} F_{\ell,m}(d\omega) \\
&\sum_{i=1}^n c_i \{e^{i\omega t_i} - 1\} \left\{ \gamma Y_{\ell}^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_i) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) \right\} \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{c}_j \{e^{-i\omega t_j} - 1\} \left\{ \gamma Y_{\ell}^m(y_j) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_j) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) \right\} \\
&+ \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_i) \right\} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{c}_j \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_j) \right\} \\
&= \sum_{\ell=\kappa}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \int_{\mathbb{R}} F_{\ell,m}(d\omega) \left| \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \{e^{i\omega t_i} - 1\} \left\{ \gamma Y_{\ell}^m(y_i) + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_i) Y_{\ell}^m(\tau_{\nu}) \right\} \right|^2 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\kappa^2} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \gamma_{\nu} q_{\nu}(y_i) \right\}^2 \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $Cov\left(X(y_i, t_i), X(y_j, t_j)\right)$ is positive semi-definite.

□